

Quantum computation with photochromic films in a Mach-Zehnder interferometer

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Abstract

Photochromic materials are of great interest because they enable the fabrication of photo-activated switches. In this study, an experiment is proposed in which two chromene-based photochromic layers were inserted into the arms of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. Chromene was studied from the perspective of optical absorption to determine the wavelength-dependent complex refractive index. Impinging ultraviolet light on one of the chromene layers induces a transition from the closed to the open form of the chromene, resulting in different phase shifts in the two arms of the interferometer. This results in a change in the probability of detecting a photon by the two detectors after the second mirror of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer. The experiment may have some interest in the fields of quantum information and quantum communications.

Keywords: Photochromic materials; Mach-Zehnder interferometer; complex refractive index.

Introduction

Interest in photochromic materials is growing in the scientific community because of their use in devices that respond to light, such as rewritable displays, dynamic optical filters and optical memories [1–4]. The photochromism of different molecules and polymers has been recently reviewed by Xu and Feringa [5]. In the phenomenon of photochromism, there is a reversible transformation induced by electromagnetic radiation, very much in the ultraviolet, from a thermodynamically more stable A isomer to a metastable B isomer [6]. Of particular interest are recent studies in which neuronal photostimulation has been demonstrated with an azobenzene-based photo-interrupter [7,8]. Chromene is a promising photochromic molecule due to the variety of its derivatives that can be synthesized [9]. Photochromic materials have been employed in Mach-Zehnder interferometers in order to build all-optical modulators [10]. Mach-Zehnder interferometers, consisting of two beam splitters, two mirrors, and two detectors, are very powerful and versatile tools for quantum optics experiments [11,12].

In this study, two chromene-based photochromic layers have been placed in the arms of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. The optical properties of chromene, in the closed and open form, has been simulated with the Hueckel theory. From the simulations, the wavelength dependent complex refractive index of the molecule has been determined. By impinging ultraviolet light on one of the chromene layer a switch from the closed form to the open form of chromene is induced, leading to different phase shifts in the two arms of the interferometers. This results in a change of the probability to detect a photon by the two detectors after the second mirror of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

Methods

To simulate the light absorption of chromene, in its closed form and its open form, the Hückel theory has been employed. The Hückel theory is a well-known molecular orbital theory in which the molecular orbitals are written as linear combination of atomic orbitals (LCAO). The approximations employed in the theory are: i) the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, with fixed nuclei positions; ii) the molecular orbitals are linear combinations of p_z orbitals, neglecting electron-electron interactions [13]. In the Hückel method, the time-independent Schrödinger equation is given by:

$$H\psi = E\psi \quad (1)$$

In this study, the Hulis package [14] has been used to define the Hamiltonian for chromene in closed and open forms. Subsequently, eigenvalues and eigenvectors have been determined. The on-site energy α is set to 0 eV and the nearest neighbour element β is set to -3 eV, in agreement with Solomon et al. [15].

To find the transition probabilities, the Fermi golden rule has been used:

$$\Gamma_{i \rightarrow j} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle \psi^j | H | \psi^i \rangle|^2 \quad (2)$$

The transition probabilities have been calculated between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the unoccupied orbitals. Gaussian peaks have been employed for the simulation of the absorption spectra, with a linewidth c of the peaks of 0.1 eV. Considering the transitions from the ground state i to the different j th excited states, the absorption coefficient can be written as:

$$\alpha(E) = \sum_j \Gamma_{i \rightarrow j} \exp\left(\frac{(E - (E_j - E_i))^2}{2c^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

To extract the imaginary part of the complex refractive index, the following expression has been used, modifying the one reported in [16]:

$$k(E) = \frac{A\alpha(E)}{4\pi} \quad (4)$$

Where A is a parameter (its value is 1×10^{15}). The real part of the complex refractive index can be derived via the Kramers-Kronig relations [17]:

$$n(\bar{\nu}) - 1 = \frac{2}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_0^\infty \frac{\omega k(\omega)}{\omega^2 - \bar{\nu}^2} d\omega \quad (5)$$

The Kramers-Kronig relations are actually Hilbert transforms [18]. For the real part of the refractive index a constant offset of 1.5 has been used as in Refs. [19,20]. Thus, it is possible to derive the complex refractive index of chromene in the open (n_{co}) and closed (n_{cc}) forms:

$$n_{co,cc}^{complex}(E) = n_{co,cc}(E) + ik_{co,cc}(E) \quad (6)$$

Results and Discussion

In Figure 1 the closed form (top) and the open form (bottom) of chromene is drawn (carbon atoms are in grey, hydrogen atoms are in light grey, and oxygen atoms are in red).

Figure 1. a) Chromene in the closed form; b) chromene in the open form (carbon atoms in grey, hydrogen atoms in light grey, oxygen atoms in red).

By employing the Hueckel method, the complex refractive index of chromene in its closed and open forms has been derived and its dependence upon the wavelength is reported in Figure 2, where black curves correspond to the real part of the refractive index and red curves correspond to the imaginary part of the refractive index.

Figure 2. Real part n (black curve) and imaginary part k (red curve) of the refractive index for chromene in the open form (n_{co} , top) and for chromene in the closed form (n_{cc} , bottom).

In Figure 3 the sketch of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer designed in this study is depicted. The interferometer consists of a photon source, two 50/50 beam splitters BS1 and BS2, two mirrors M. and two detectors D1 and D2. The two layers of chromene are indicated with PCx (along the x direction after the beam splitter BS1) and PCy (along the y direction after the beam splitter BS1). The thickness of the chromene layer is 75 nm.

Figure 3. Sketch of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer with the photon source and the two detectors D1 and D2, the two mirrors M, the two 50/50 beam splitters BS1 and BS2, and the two photochromic layers PCx (along the x direction transmitted by BS1) and PCy (along the y direction reflected by BS1).

The state vectors and operators are adopted in agreement with Ref. [12]. The photon moving along the x axis is represented by the state vector:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

While the photon moving on the y axis is represented by the state vector:

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The two mirrors are represented by the operator:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The two beam splitters are represented by the operator:

$$BS = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & i \\ i & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

A 90-degree phase shift is assigned to reflection. The chromene-based photochromic (PC) layer is represented by the operator:

$$PC = \begin{bmatrix} \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi d n_{co,cc}^{complex}}{\lambda}\right) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi d n_{co,cc}^{complex}}{\lambda}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

With d the thickness of the layer.

Without the chromene-based photochromic layers in the Mach-Zehnder interferometer, the probability to measure the photon with the detectors D1 is:

$$D1 = |x^T BS M BSx|^2 \quad (12)$$

While the probability to measure the photon with the detectors D2 is:

$$D2 = |y^T BS M BSx|^2 \quad (13)$$

x^T is the transpose of vector x , while y^T is the transpose of vector y . The photon will be detected by D1. Thus $D1 = 1$, while $D2 = 0$.

With the chromene-based photochromic layers in the Mach-Zehnder interferometer, the probability to measure the photon with the detectors D1 is:

$$D1_{PC} = |x^T BS M PC BSx|^2 \quad (14)$$

While the probability to measure the photon with the detectors D2 is:

$$D2_{PC} = |y^T BS M PC BSx|^2 \quad (15)$$

With both the chromene layers with the molecule in the closed form, or open form, the probabilities at the two detectors are again $D1 = 1$ and $D2 = 0$.

By impinging the chromene layer PCy with ultraviolet light the chromene switches to the open form with a consequent change of its refractive index (n_{co} , Figure 2 top), while chromene in PCx keeps being in its closed form (with refractive index n_{cc} , Figure 2 bottom). Because of the different refractive indexes of the two layers PCx and PCy, the phase shifts will be different in the two arms of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer. In the case of a photon at a wavelength of 454 nm, the probabilities at the two detectors are $D1 = 0.853$ and $D2 = 0.147$. Since the complex refractive index of chromene in its closed and open forms is wavelength dependent, such probabilities will consequently depend upon the photon wavelength.

Conclusion

In this work, two chromene-based photochromic layers were inserted into the arms of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. The absorption of light by chromene was studied by Hueckel theory, consequently determining the complex, wavelength-dependent refractive index. Impacting ultraviolet light on one of the chromene layers induces a transition from the closed to the open form of the chromene, resulting in different phase shifts in the two arms of the interferometer. This results in a change in the probability of detecting a photon by the two detectors after the second mirror of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer. Such an experiment may be of interest to the scientific community working in quantum information and quantum communications.

Appendix

Hamiltonian of chromene in its closed form:

	1 C	2 C	3 O	4 C	5 C	6 C	7 C	8 C	9 C	10 C	
1 C	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
2 C	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		0,66 β	0,00 β						
3 O	0,00 β	0,66 β	$\alpha + 2,09\beta$		0,66 β	0,00 β					
4 C	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,66 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β
5 C	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
6 C	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
7 C	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
8 C	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β					
9 C	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β						
10 C	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$	

Hamiltonian of chromene in its open form:

	1 C	2 C	3 C	4 C	5 C	6 C	7 O	8 C	9 C	10 C	
1 C	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
2 C	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β						
3 C	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β					
4 C	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β				
5 C	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	1,06 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
6 C	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		0,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
7 O	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β	1,06 β	0,00 β	$\alpha + 0,97\beta$		0,00 β	0,00 β	0,00 β
8 C	0,00 β	1,00 β	0,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β	0,00 β				
9 C	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$		1,00 β						
10 C	0,00 β	1,00 β	$\alpha + 0,00\beta$								

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References

- [1] H. Torres-Pierna, D. Ruiz-Molina, C. Roscini, Highly transparent photochromic films with a tunable and fast solution-like response, *Mater. Horiz.* 7 (2020) 2749–2759. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0MH01073A>.
- [2] V.A. Barachevsky, Advances in photonics of organic photochromism, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry* 354 (2018) 61–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2017.06.034>.
- [3] G. Naren, C.-W. Hsu, S. Li, M. Morimoto, S. Tang, J. Hernando, G. Guirado, M. Irie, F.M. Raymo, H. Sundén, J. Andréasson, An all-photonics full color RGB system based on molecular photoswitches, *Nat Commun* 10 (2019) 3996. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-11885-4>.
- [4] V. Castaing, L. Giordano, C. Richard, D. Gourier, M. Allix, B. Viana, Photochromism and Persistent Luminescence in Ni-Doped ZnGa₂O₄ Transparent Glass-Ceramics: Toward Optical Memory Applications, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 125 (2021) 10110–10120. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.1c01900>.
- [5] F. Xu, B.L. Feringa, Photoresponsive Supramolecular Polymers: From Light-Controlled Small Molecules to Smart Materials, *Advanced Materials* 35 (2023) 2204413. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202204413>.
- [6] J. Boelke, S. Hecht, Designing Molecular Photoswitches for Soft Materials Applications, *Advanced Optical Materials* 7 (2019) 1900404. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adom.201900404>.
- [7] M.L. DiFrancesco, F. Lodola, E. Colombo, L. Maragliano, M. Bramini, G.M. Paternò, P. Baldelli, M.D. Serra, L. Lunelli, M. Marchioretto, G. Grasselli, S. Cimò, L. Colella, D. Fazzi, F. Ortica, V. Vurro, C.G. Eleftheriou, D. Shmal, J.F. Maya-Vetencourt, C. Bertarelli, G. Lanzani, F. Benfenati, Neuronal firing modulation by a membrane-targeted photoswitch, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 15 (2020) 296–306. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-019-0632-6>.
- [8] G.M. Paternò, E. Colombo, V. Vurro, F. Lodola, S. Cimò, V. Sesti, E. Molotokaite, M. Bramini, L. Ganzer, D. Fazzi, C. D'Andrea, F. Benfenati, C. Bertarelli, G. Lanzani, Membrane Environment Enables Ultrafast Isomerization of Amphiphilic Azobenzene, *Advanced Science* 7 (2020) 1903241. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.201903241>.
- [9] P.S. Perevozchikova, T.M. Aliev, P.A. Nikitina, N.E. Shepel, Synthesis and Photochromic Properties of a Novel Chromene Derivative, *INEOS OPEN* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.32931/io2102a>.
- [10] J.-W. Kang, J.-J. Kim, E. Kim, All-optical Mach–Zehnder modulator using a photochromic dye-doped polymer, *Applied Physics Letters* 80 (2002) 1710–1712. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1459111>.
- [11] M. Hajdušek, R. Van Meter, *Quantum Communications*, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.02367>.
- [12] F. Rioux, 8.86: Simulating a Quantum Computer with a Mach-Zehnder Interferometer, *Chemistry LibreTexts* (2019). [https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Physical_and_Theoretical_Chemistry_Textbook_Maps/Quantum_Tutorials_\(Rioux\)/08%3A_Quantum_Teleportation/8.86%3A_Simulating_a_Quantum_Computer_with_a_Mach-Zehnder_Interferometer](https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Physical_and_Theoretical_Chemistry_Textbook_Maps/Quantum_Tutorials_(Rioux)/08%3A_Quantum_Teleportation/8.86%3A_Simulating_a_Quantum_Computer_with_a_Mach-Zehnder_Interferometer) (accessed February 27, 2024).
- [13] G. Guy Robert, V.V. Troy, *Physical Chemistry*, MIT OpenCourseWare (n.d.). <https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/chemistry/5-61-physical-chemistry-fall-2007/> (accessed February 5, 2022).
- [14] Huckel Theory and HuLiS: a calculator that also describes mesomerism., (2013). <http://www.hulis.free.fr/> (accessed June 8, 2020).
- [15] G.C. Solomon, J.P. Bergfield, C.A. Stafford, M.A. Ratner, When “small” terms matter: Coupled interference features in the transport properties of cross-conjugated molecules, *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology* 2 (2011) 862–871. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.2.95>.

- [16] R. Kohandani, S.S. Saini, Extracting optical absorption characteristics from semiconductor nanowire arrays, *Nanotechnology* 33 (2022) 395204. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/ac74cc>.
- [17] J.I. Pankove, *Optical processes in semiconductors*, Unabridged republication, with slight corrections, Dover Publications, Inc, New York, 1975.
- [18] J.F. Ogilvie, G.J. Fee, Equivalence of Kramers-Kronig and Fourier Transforms to Convert between Optical Dispersion and Optical Spectra, *MATCH* 69 (2013) 249–262.
- [19] C. Wiebeler, C.A. Bader, C. Meier, S. Schumacher, Optical spectrum, perceived color, refractive index, and non-adiabatic dynamics of the photochromic diarylethene CMTE, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 16 (2014) 14531–14538. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3CP55490B>.
- [20] F. Scotognella, Multilayer plasmonic photonic structures embedding photochromic molecules or optical gain molecules, *Physica E: Low-Dimensional Systems and Nanostructures* (2020) 114081. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2020.114081>.